

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Pan, T. H., & Lin, Y. N. (2022). Organizational Commitment Impact on Job Well-Being of SME Employees in Taiwan in Post-COVID-19 Era. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 5(1), 97-112.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.05.01.407

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Economics and Business* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Journal of Economics and Business* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Economics and Business, which includes, but is not limited to, Business Economics (Micro and Macro), Finance, Management, Marketing, Business Law, Entrepreneurship, Behavioral and Health Economics, Government Taxation and Regulations, Financial Markets, International Economics, Investment, and Economic Development. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Economics and Business* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Economics and Business.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Organizational Commitment Impact on Job Well-Being of SMEs Employees in Taiwan in Post-COVID-19 Era

Te-Han Pan¹, Yao-Nan Lin²

¹ Graduate Institute of Business Administration, College of Management, Fu Jen Catholic University, New Taipei City 242062, Taiwan; Email: gthank2000@gmail.com

² Department of Business Administration, Fu Jen Catholic University, New Taipei City 242062, Taiwan; Email: yaonan1208@hotmail.com

Correspondence: Te-Han Pan. Email: gthank2000@gmail.com

Abstract

Taiwan's industrial structure is mainly composed of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), with over 98% of enterprises being SMEs and employing more than 80% of the workforce in Taiwan. Many industries are under severe stress due to the COVID-19 outbreak, and many companies are reducing staff hiring or staff working hours. The main purpose of this study was to examine the factors influencing the job well-being of Taiwanese SME employees in the context of the COVID-19 epidemic, including organizational justice, job insecurity, decent work, and organizational commitment. Through a questionnaire survey, 653 valid questionnaires were collected and analyzed using structural equation modeling to verify the effects between the study constructs. The study found that organizational justice, job insecurity, and decent work all had significant effects on organizational commitment, with job insecurity having the least effect. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employees' job well-being, with a standardized regression coefficient of 0.469. In the research model, the R² of employees' organizational justice, job insecurity, decent work, and organizational commitment on job well-being was as high as 0.724. The results of the study show that Taiwan has a large number of SMEs that can respond quickly and flexibly to the environment. Even in the unsettled environment of an epidemic, employees' organizational commitment to the company remains a decisive factor in employee well-being. The smaller-than-expected impact of employee job insecurity is indirect evidence of the resilience of the Taiwanese industry.

Keywords: COVID-19, Job Well-Being, Organizational Justice, Job Insecurity, Decent Work, Organizational Commitment, Taiwan SMEs

1. Introduction

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Taiwan are the main driving force of the country's economic development and play a key role in sustaining Taiwan's economic growth, providing employment opportunities, and developing industries (Lin & Lai, 2020). The adaptability of SMEs and their sensitivity to changes (Jankelova et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2017). The flexibility of SMEs and the composition of the industrial supply chain are the competitive advantages of Taiwan's high-tech industry (Hou, 2020). The development of Taiwan's SMEs has a significant impact on the country's competitiveness (Yang & Chuang, 2020). In 2020, the number of SMEs in

Taiwan was 1,548,835, accounting for 98.93% of all enterprises; the number of employed persons in SMEs reached 9,311,000, accounting for 80.94% of the total number of employed persons in Taiwan. The sales volume of SMEs is 23 trillion 555.513 billion yuan, accounting for more than 50% of the total sales volume of all enterprises (Small and Medium Enterprises Division, 2021).

In order to survive the COVID-19 global epidemic, small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan have resorted to temporary work stoppages, layoffs, partial business hours, and hiring temporary staff in response (Zhou, 2020). Due to the small size of SMEs, the financial strength and stability of enterprises are relatively poor, and they are more vulnerable to the impact of the general environment (Lu et al., 2020). Although in most cases, human resources are often seen as the easiest way to reduce costs, especially in difficult times (Cao et al., 2019). If employees choose to leave the company under the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic, the competitive advantage of SMEs will be rapidly reduced. Retaining employees is very important to a company, especially in small and medium-sized businesses, where employees choose to leave, resulting in a loss of expertise, competitiveness, and experience (Ponnu & Chuah, 2010). How to retain employees is an issue of concern to SMEs (Burhan et al., 2021).

Employees are the most valuable assets of a modern enterprise, and motivated, professional and loyal employees are the key to a company's competitiveness in the market (Gabčanová, 2011; Imamoglu et al., 2019). Therefore, companies should pay attention to the happiness of their employees at work. Among other things, employees' perceived organizational justice will generate positive attitudes and behaviors at work (Khan et al., 2015). When employees perceive that the organization is failing to deliver on its promises or treating employees unfairly, their behavior will be negative (Cohen & Diamant, 2019; Hussain & Shahzad, 2021). Moreover, psychological insecurity at work affects employees' attitudes, and performance (Salas-Nicas et al., 2020). Even before COVID-19, modern SMEs were often uncertain due to technological innovations, global trends, and rapid market changes, and were unable to provide a stable employment environment for their employees (Etehad & Karatepe, 2019; Jung et al., 2021). Furthermore, the International Labour Organization (1999) uses the term decent work to ensure decent working conditions for all employees in every country. In Taiwan, employees of small and medium-sized enterprises are often considered to have less stable job security. Therefore, the physical aspect of labor should be considered as a factor affecting employees' happiness at work.

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the influencing factors affecting job well-being under COVID-19 for employees in small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan. Through literature exploration and analysis, the study proposed a research model that includes organizational justice, job insecurity, decent work, and organizational commitment to analyze the influencing mechanisms affecting job well-being. Then, after referring to relevant literature, this study developed a quantitative questionnaire to collect research data from employees in Taiwan SMEs. The data were then analyzed using a structural equation model, and the results of the study could be used as a reference for senior executives of small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan to enhance employees' happiness at work.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is a very important topic in organizational behavior research (Holbrook Jr, 2002; Jones & Skarlicki, 2003). It is the employees who perceive how the organization treats them fairly (De Cremer et al., 2010) and an important interpersonal perception that employees receive from the organization and their supervisors. When an organization treats its employees with respect and dignity, employees tend to be more accepting and tolerant of the organization in terms of a sense of justice (Wang et al., 2019). Previous research has shown that perceptions of justice by colleagues and supervisors play an important role in efficient and effective collaboration. When employees feel organizational justice, it will increase their commitment to work. When employees' perception of organizational justice increases, their work engagement also increases (Cropanzano et al., 2007), also work satisfaction (Konovsky, 2000; Lin, 2015).

In the working environment of small and medium-sized enterprises, it is easy for the boss's family members or friends and relatives to work together. It is very important for the employees to feel the fair treatment of the organization. The employees' perception of the organization justice is can be defined as their own perception of the difficulty of the work tasks, the responsibility of the work, and the performance of the work compared to their remuneration.

2.2 Job Well-Being

The pursuit of well-being can be said to be the goal of all human activities. Subjective well-being describes how people perceive their lives and life experiences (Diener, 1984). It is a multidimensional concept that includes life satisfaction, positive or negative emotional impact (Diener et al., 1999). Research on well-being is extremely rich and can be divided into two major schools of thought: subjective well-being and psychological well-being (Diao & Chen, 2020). Job well-being is the result of the interaction between organizational environment and personal characteristics, which is the positive or negative emotions felt by employees in the pursuit of self-worth. Naturally, well-being at work is also a goal that Taiwanese SME employees seek in their organizations.

When employees are respected in the workplace, they show more subjective work well-being, are more courteous to other employees and are more helpful and supportive of their co-workers, which are useful to supervisors/managers and the organization (Abid et al., 2020). Moreover, employee well-being is a key goal for organizations to consider because it is not only an outcome, but a prerequisite that can impact many organizational goals, such as creativity, productivity, workplace collaboration, and increased social capital (Agarwal, 2021). However, in the COVID-19 environment, employees are worried and anxious about the impact of the epidemic, which inevitably leads to some psychological stress and affects their sense of well-being at work (Russo et al., 2021).

There have been many studies on job well-being in the past, and scholars have explored different factors affecting job well-being in many different industries, such as organizational support, job competency (Diao & Chen, 2020), perceived organizational justice (Abid et al., 2020), organizational commitment (Jain et al., 2019), workplace health promotion (Gorgenyi-Hegyey et al., 2021), life well-being (Weziak-Bialowolska et al., 2020), and so on. According to the above literature, employees' perceived organizational justice significantly affects job well-being, that is, in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan, when employees perceive higher organizational justice, their job well-being should also be higher. Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypothesis.

H1: The perceived organizational justice of Taiwan SMEs employees will positively and significantly affect their job well-being

2.3 Organizational Commitment

In their 1991 study, Meyer and Allen pointed out that organizational commitment is developed from work experience. Employees are more attached to organizations if the organization can meet their needs. Work experience can be divided into meeting the need for job comfort and meeting the need to be competent in the job role (Meyer & Allen, 1991). In this context, emotional commitment is defined as an emotional or affective attachment to the organization, when the organization is recognized, participated, and enjoyed by the individual as part of the organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990). This organizational commitment enhances employee performance, organizational citizenship, and job satisfaction, and reduces absenteeism and turnover rates (Cohen, 2017; Meyer et al., 1989; Riketta, 2002; Tett & Meyer, 1993; Yiing & Ahmad, 2009). In the Taiwan SME work environment, the human connection is often very close. Especially under the influence of Eastern collectivist culture, organizational commitment works on multiple aspects of employees, whether it is emotional awareness, employee performance, or even job satisfaction. In the context of Taiwanese SMEs, organizational commitment has been shown to have a positive and significant impact on organizational effectiveness (Tseng, 2010).

Moreover, Kim and Milliman's (2021) study confirms that employee perceptions of corporate social responsibility positively influence organizational commitment through organizational procedural justice and organizational-oriented self-esteem. Then, Wang, Guchait, and Back (2019) also verified that employees' perceived justice would affect organizational commitment. Therefore, if the employees' perceived justice is higher, their organizational commitment also will be higher. The following hypothesis is proposed.

H2: The perceived organizational justice of Taiwan SMEs employees will positively and significantly affect their perceived organizational commitment

2.4 Job Insecurity

Many authors define job insecurity as the expectation of employees that they will continue to work (Hartley et al., 1990; Heaney et al., 1994; Witte, 1999), while other authors define job insecurity as employees' perceptions of the likelihood of losing their jobs in times of crisis (Mohr, 2000). According to Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (1984), job insecurity consists of two important factors, namely, the severity of threats and feelings of powerlessness. Powerlessness occurs when individuals believe they are incapable of resisting threats to continuity and is considered a fundamental variable of job insecurity because it exacerbates the threats experienced by the individual (Koo et al., 2021). Powerlessness occurs when individuals believe they are incapable of resisting threats to continuity and can worsen personal perceptions, such as the threat of a declining economic environment brought about by COVID-19, and employee powerlessness can arise. It has been confirmed that job insecurity can lead to negative attitudinal responses, including increased willingness to leave, reduced organizational commitment, and job satisfaction (Ashford et al., 1989). In addition, job insecurity can lead to serious physical and mental health complications such as heart disease, insomnia, and mental distress, and contribute to the persistent poor health status of employees (Smith, 2017).

Moreover, Frone's study, which explored the relationship between employees' perceptions of job insecurity, health, and organizational commitment in the context of the U.S. recession, confirmed that employees' job insecurity negatively affects their perceptions of organizational commitment (Frone, 2018). Then, Huang, et. al. examined the effects of job insecurity and organizational commitment on organizational initiative and individual practice concerning employees' age. The results demonstrated that employee job insecurity harmed organizational commitment in both qualitative and quantitative studies (G. h. Huang et al., 2021). Also, a study by Diao et al. confirmed that job insecurity negatively affects employees' job well-being (Diao & Chen, 2020). Then, Darvishmotevali and Ali found that job insecurity reduces employees' subjective well-being and negatively affects their job performance (Darvishmotevali & Ali, 2020).

In short, from the above literature, it can be found that employees' perception of job insecurity will negatively affect their perception of organizational commitment to the company. In addition, when employees feel more insecure about their jobs, their sense of well-being at work decreases. Under the pressure and influence brought by COVID-19, employees' perception of job insecurity will negatively affect their perception of corporate commitment and job well-being in Taiwan SMEs. Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypothesis.

H3: The perceived job insecurity of Taiwan SMEs employees will negatively and significantly affect their perceived organizational commitment

H4: The perceived job insecurity of Taiwan SMEs employees will negatively and significantly affect their perceived job well-being

2.5 Decent Work

The International Labor Organization (ILO) explicitly defines decent labor as that decent work describes what employees expect from their jobs and encompasses opportunities for work, fair income, workplace safety, and social protection for families. Work should provide for employees' personal development and social integration, allow employees to express ideas and participate in organizational decisions that affect their lives, and provide for

equal treatment of men and women (ILO, 2020). Therefore, a large number of interdisciplinary studies from the fields of public health, public policy, economics, and government have focused on the acquisition of decent work and its effects on the physical and mental health of individuals (Blustein et al., 2016; Duffy et al., 2021). In Psychology of Working Theory (PWT), Duffy divides decent work into five components: interpersonal and physically safe working conditions, access to health care, adequate compensation, leisure time off, and values that match family and cultural values. Four variables, such as economic constraints, marginalization, work willingness, and occupational adaptability, predict the security of decent work (Duffy et al., 2016). Most of the employees in Taiwan's SMEs work in nearby suitable enterprises in order to earn a living. Decent work can be said to be the basic expectation of an employee's career. The work is meaningful, well paid, and can meet the expectations and wishes of the general public.

A study by Huang, Shen, and Yuan in 2021 identified that employees' perceived decent work affects perceptions of organizational commitment in emotional terms and explored the role of psychological safety and the scope of employee relationships (W. Huang et al., 2021). Then, Hanaysha's research confirms that the work environment has a positive effect on organizational commitment and that employees' perceptions of the work environment affect their job satisfaction and commitment to the organization (Hanaysha, 2016). Therefore, when employees' perception of decent work is higher, their perception of organizational commitment is also higher. Similarly, when employees feel that the more decent work they do, the higher their happiness at work will be.

Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypotheses.

H5: The perceived decent work of Taiwan SMEs employees will positively and significantly affect their perceived organizational commitment

H6: The perceived decent work of Taiwan SMEs employees will positively and significantly affect their perceived job well-being

Moreover, when employees' perception of organizational commitment is higher, their happiness at work is also higher. Boyd and Nowell (2020) demonstrated that employees' perceptions of community, community responsibility, organizational commitment and identification, and public service motivation positively and significantly affect their job well-being. From the literature, it can be inferred that the higher the perceived organizational commitment of the employees in Taiwan SMEs, the higher their happiness at work will be. Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypotheses.

H7: The perceived organizational commitment of Taiwan SMEs employees will positively and significantly affect their perceived job well-being

2.6 Mediating Effects

This study proposes that the factors that affect the organizational commitment of employees in Taiwan SMEs include organizational justice, job insecurity, and decent work and that organizational commitment positively affects employees' job well-being. Therefore, this study proposes that there is a mediating effect between organizational justice, job insecurity, decent work, organizational commitment, and job well-being. That is, organizational justice, job insecurity, and decent work affect employees' job well-being through their perception of organizational commitment. This study, therefore, proposes the hypothesis of the mediating effect study underneath.

H8: Perceived organizational justice of employees in Taiwanese SMEs affects their well-being at work through their organizational commitment

H9: Perceived job insecurity of employees in Taiwanese SMEs affects their well-being at work through their organizational commitment

H10: Perceived decent work of employees in Taiwanese SMEs affects their well-being at work through their organizational commitment

The research model for this study is shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research model.

3. Research Design

3.1 Data Collection

The study focused on the mechanism by which employees' work happiness is affected by organizational commitment under the impact of COVID-19 in Taiwan's SMEs. According to the above statistics, the total number of employees of SMEs in Taiwan is about 9.3 million. According to the sample calculator on The Survey System website, a valid sample of 384 is required for a confidence level of 95% and a confidence interval of 5%. In this study, an e-questionnaire was created through google form and distributed through social media friend groups from 2021/8/30 to 2021/10/1 by convenience sampling. 653 questionnaires were collected and 631 valid questionnaires were obtained by removing invalid questionnaires. The sample size of this study met the required requirements.

3.2 Instrument Measurement

The study variables include demographic variables such as gender, age, position, education, and years of experience, and research variables such as organizational justice, job insecurity, decent work, organizational commitment, job well-being, and colleague territorial behavior. The following section describes the development of the questionnaire questions for the study components.

The organizational justice dimension is based on the study of Jang et al. (2021), which analyzed the impact of organizational justice on organizational commitment. The organizational justice dimension consists of two sub-dimensions, distributive justice, and procedural justice, of which the four questions on distributive justice are adapted to fit the topic of this study. The operational definition of organizational Justice in this study is that employees' self-perceived job performance, taking into account the difficulties and responsibilities of the job, is adequately remunerated compared to other employees in similar jobs.

Secondly, organizational commitment is based on Yeh and Chen's study on the relationship between pay confidentiality, distributive justice, and work-related outcomes (Yeh & Chen, 2017), where the organizational commitment construct provides six questions that are adapted to the context of this study. The operational definition of organizational commitment in this study is that employees care about the fate of the organization, are

willing to do their best to help the company succeed, and are willing to accept any type of work within the organization.

In addition, the job insecurity construct was adapted from Chen and Eyoun's study on job insecurity and emotional exhaustion among restaurant workers at one point in the post-COVID-19 era (Chen & Eyoun, 2021). The operational definition of job insecurity in this study was that employees felt that they would soon lose their jobs, were worried that they might not be able to keep their jobs, felt uneasy about their jobs, and felt that they might lose their jobs soon.

In the context of decent work, this study draws on Vignoli et al. (2020) to examine the context, conceptualization, and evaluation of decent work in France, where decent work consists of physical and interpersonal safety working conditions, healthcare, work remuneration, free time and rest and complementary values. One question was used for health care, one question was used for leisure time and rest, and one question was used in the matching of organizational and individual family value houses, which was adapted to the context of this study, making a total of seven questions. The operational definition of decent labor in this study is that employees feel safe at work, free from emotional or verbal abuse, have adequate health care, adequate rest, and values that match those of the organization.

Next, in terms of well-being at work, according to Pradhan and Hati (2019) in the development and validation of the Employee Well-being at Work Scale, there are sub-schemes of mental health, social well-being, workplace well-being, and subjective well-being. This study used nine questions from their workplace well-being sub-schemes and adapted them to the appropriate questions. The operational definition of workplace well-being in this study is that employees are satisfied with their jobs, feel that their jobs are meaningful, value their jobs, have a good workplace, have future development, maintain a balance with their family life, believe that their bosses care about them, and believe that their jobs can improve their skills.

In terms of co-worker territorial behavior, this study adopted the works of Brown (2009), in which the co-worker territorial behavior constructs include identity, personal likes and interests, and domain sub-constructs concerning the territoriality of the workplace, and five questions were developed to measure co-worker territorial behavior regarding all the constructs. The operational definition is that colleagues bring in personally meaningful photos, coffee mugs, books, stationery, place their hobbies and interests in the workplace, create borders and label their work area with their names.

3.3 Data analysis

The data analysis for this study was divided into three stages, the first stage was a descriptive statistical analysis, the second stage was a test model validation and the third stage was a structural equation analysis. A 7-point Likert scale was used to measure each questionnaire item. Firstly, statistical analysis was conducted on the personal data of the sample, including gender, age, position, education level, and years of experience. Item reliability, construct reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity were included in the measurement model validation. Model fit analysis was conducted before structural equation model validation to confirm that the number of model variables was appropriate to the sample size. The structural equation model is measured using path analysis for the regression coefficients. Explanatory force analysis is also carried out depending on the variance of the variables.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

The gender of the respondents was mainly male, a total of 321, accounting for 50.9%; the position was mainly junior staff, a total of 370, accounting for 58.6%; the education level was mainly university, 242 respondents, accounting for 38.4%; the age was mainly under 30 years old, 182 respondents, accounting for 28.8%; the working experience was mainly 10-20 years, 159 respondents, accounting for 25.2%, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistical analysis

Variable	Category	Amount	Percentage	Variable	Category	Amount	Percentage
Gender	Female	310	49.1	Age	Under 30 years old	182	28.8
	Male	321	50.9		31-40 years old	179	28.4
Position	Mid-Manager	94	14.9	Work experience	41-50 years old	149	23.6
	Senior-Manager	68	10.8		51-60 years old	106	16.8
	junior staff	370	58.6		Over 61 years old	15	2.4
	Others	99	15.7		Under 3 years	150	23.8
Education	Under junior high	33	5.2	Work experience	3-5 years	95	15.1
	Senior high	179	28.4		6-10 years	137	21.7
	College	78	12.4		10-20 years	159	25.2
	University	242	38.4		Over 21 years	90	14.3
	Graduate and above	99	15.7				

4.2 Convergent Validity

As in Table 2, all standardized factor loadings of questions are from 0.632 to 0.932 falling into a reasonable range. This demonstrates all questions have convergent validity. All the composite reliability of the constructs ranging from 0.857 to 0.953; exceed 0.7 recommended by Nunnally (1994) indicating all constructs have internal consistency. Lastly, all average variance extracted (AVE) ranging from 0.547 to 0.836, exceed 0.5 suggested by Hair et al. (1998) and Fornell and Larcker (1981) showing all constructs have adequate convergent validity.

Table 2: Results for the convergent validity

Construct	Item	Significance of estimated parameters				Item Reliability		Construct Reliability CR	Convergence validity AVE
		Unstd.	S.E.	Unstd./S.E.	p-value	Std.	SMC		
OJ	OJ1	1.000				0.932	0.869	0.953	0.836
	OJ2	0.956	0.024	39.971	0.000	0.907	0.823		
	OJ3	0.987	0.023	42.278	0.000	0.927	0.859		
	OJ4	0.950	0.025	37.342	0.000	0.891	0.794		
OC	OC1	1.000				0.731	0.534	0.880	0.552
	OC2	1.012	0.049	20.818	0.000	0.825	0.681		
	OC3	1.274	0.072	17.630	0.000	0.775	0.601		
	OC4	1.168	0.070	16.768	0.000	0.708	0.501		
	OC5	1.116	0.064	17.444	0.000	0.764	0.584		
	OC6	0.746	0.047	15.763	0.000	0.643	0.413		
JI	JI1	1.000				0.892	0.796	0.932	0.773
	JI2	1.016	0.028	36.236	0.000	0.924	0.854		
	JI3	0.959	0.037	26.258	0.000	0.799	0.638		
	JI4	0.981	0.030	33.142	0.000	0.897	0.805		
DW	DW1	1.000				0.724	0.524	0.857	0.547
	DW2	1.336	0.065	20.521	0.000	0.856	0.733		
	DW3	0.981	0.056	17.610	0.000	0.734	0.539		
	DW5	0.947	0.064	14.772	0.000	0.648	0.420		

Construct	Item	Significance of estimated parameters				Item Reliability		Construct Reliability	Convergence validity
		Unstd.	S.E.	Unstd./S.E.	p-value	Std.	SMC	CR	AVE
	DW6	1.092	0.068	16.157	0.000	0.719	0.517		
JWB	JWB1	1.000				0.832	0.692	0.916	0.550
	JWB2	0.758	0.041	18.566	0.000	0.661	0.437		
	JWB3	0.560	0.031	17.908	0.000	0.652	0.425		
	JWB4	0.643	0.038	17.083	0.000	0.632	0.399		
	JWB5	0.984	0.041	24.024	0.000	0.803	0.645		
	JWB6	1.007	0.040	25.135	0.000	0.834	0.696		
	JWB7	0.839	0.047	17.939	0.000	0.650	0.423		
	JWB8	1.160	0.050	23.091	0.000	0.782	0.612		
	JWB9	0.900	0.039	22.915	0.000	0.786	0.618		

Note: Unstd.= Unstandardized factor loadings; Std = Standardized factor loadings; SMC = Square Multiple Correlations; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; OJ=Organizational justice; OC=Organizational commitment; JI=Job insecurity; DW=Decent work; JWB=Job wellbeing.

4.3 Discriminant validity

For the discriminant validity, the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) of a given construct was compared with the correlations between the construct and the other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). If the square root of the AVE of a construct is greater than the off-diagonal elements in the corresponding rows and columns, implying the indicators are more closely related to the construct than the others. As in Table 3, the bold numbers in the diagonal direction represent the square roots of AVEs. Because most of the numbers in the diagonal direction are greater than the off-diagonal numbers, discriminant validity appears to be satisfactory for all constructs.

Table 3: Discriminant validity for the measurement model

	AVE	OJ	OC	JI	DW	JWB
OJ	0.836	0.914				
OC	0.552	0.532	0.743			
JI	0.773	-0.379	-0.274	0.879		
DW	0.547	0.494	0.568	-0.298	0.740	
JWB	0.550	0.638	0.769	-0.376	0.683	0.742

Note: The items on the diagonal in bold represent the square roots of the AVE; off-diagonal elements are the correlation estimates. OJ=Organizational justice; OC=Organizational commitment; JI=Job insecurity; DW=Decent work; JWB=Job wellbeing.

4.4 Model fit

In this study, the model fitness metrics were based on the 194 SSCI papers examined in Jackson et al. (2009), which were used as the blueprint for the applied model fitness analysis. The Bollen-Stine Bootstrap correction model was used to correct for poor fit as SEM samples larger than 200 tend to have large cardinality values (Bollen & Stine, 1992). After the Bollen-Stine Bootstrap correction, all the fitness indicators of the study passed, indicating that the results of the study were acceptable. Table 4 shows the results of model fitness as below.

Table 4: Model fitness

Fit Indices	Criteria	Fitness
Chi-square		642.483
Degree of freedom		454
CFI	>.9	0.987

Fit Indices	Criteria	Fitness
RMSEA	<.08	0.026
TLI	>.9	0.986
GFI	>.9	0.958
NFI	>.9	0.958
χ^2/df	<3	1.415
AGFI	>.8	0.949

Note: CFI = Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index; GFI = Goodness of Fit Index; NFI = Normed-fit index; AGFI = Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index.

4.5 Path analysis

Table 5 shows the results of path coefficients. Organizational justice and decent work have a significant impact on organizational commitment. The standardized regression coefficients are 0.199 and 0.391. Then, organizational justice and decent work have a significant impact on organizational commitment. The standardized regression coefficients values are 0.199 and 0.391. Moreover, organizational justice, organizational commitment, job insecurity, and decent work all have a significant impact on job well-being. The standardized regression coefficients are 0.168, 0.591, -0.063 and 0.353. The results support the research question regarding the validity of the research model. 40.7% of organizational commitment can be explained by organizational justice and decent work. 72.4% of job well-being can be explained by organizational justice, organizational commitment, and decent work.

Table 5: Regression coefficient

DV	IV	Unstd	S.E.	Unstd./S.E.	p-value	Std.	R ²
OC	OJ	0.199	0.028	7.060	0.000	0.322	0.407
	JI	-0.020	0.024	-0.831	0.406	-0.033	
	DW	0.391	0.049	7.970	0.000	0.399	
JWB	OJ	0.168	0.027	6.140	0.000	0.216	0.724
	OC	0.591	0.056	10.510	0.000	0.469	
	JI	-0.063	0.023	-2.797	0.005	-0.080	
	DW	0.353	0.049	7.228	0.000	0.286	

Note: OJ=Organizational justice; OC=Organizational commitment; JI=Job insecurity; DW=Decent work; JWB=Job well-being.

Figure 2 displays the SEM statistics model as the following.

Figure 2: SEM statistics model diagram

Note: OJ=Organization justice; OC=Organizational commitment; JI=Job insecurity; DW=Decent work; JWB=Job wellbeing.

4.6 Mediation Effects

As shown in Table 6, the indirect effect OJ→OC→JWB, $p < 0.05$, bias-corrected confidence interval (CI) does not include 0 (CI of OJ→OC→JWB= [0.062 0.200]). The existence of indirect effect was supported. Then, the indirect effect JI→OC→JWB, $p > 0.05$, bias-corrected confidence interval (CI) does include 0 (CI of JI→OC→JWB= [-0.048 0.022]). The existence of indirect effect was rejected. Moreover, the indirect effect DW→OC→JWB, $p < 0.05$, bias-corrected confidence interval (CI) does not include 0 (CI of DW→OC→JWB= [0.151 0.356]). The existence of total effect was supported.

Table 6: The analysis of indirect effects

Effect	Point Estimate	product of coefficients			Bootstrap 1000 times Bias-corrected 95%	
		S.E.	Z-Value	p-value	Lower bound	Upper bound
indirect effect						
OJ→OC→JWB	0.117	0.035	3.374	0.001	0.062	0.200
JI→OC→JWB	-0.012	0.017	-0.699	0.484	-0.048	0.022
DW→OC→JWB	0.231	0.053	4.393	0.000	0.151	0.356

Note: OJ=Organization justice; OC=Organizational commitment; JI=Job insecurity; DW=Decent work; JWB=Job wellbeing;

5. Conclusion and discussion

The study examines the factors affecting employees' job well-being, including organizational justice, job insecurity, decent labor, and organizational commitment, and also considers the moderating effect of colleagues' territorial behavior, in the context of the changing economic environment after the global COVID-19 epidemic, in the context

of small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan. Through the results of the questionnaire survey, the research contribution is as follows.

(1) Organizational justice and decent work significantly affect employees' organizational commitment

For Taiwan SMEs employees, the standardized regression coefficients of organizational justice and decent work are 0.322 and 0.399 for the influence of organizational commitment. This means that employees' perceptions of justice treatment by the organization enhance their perceptions of organizational commitment and that employees' perceptions of decent work have a greater impact on their organizational commitment than their perceptions of organizational justice. The results of this study revealed that SMEs employees cared a lot about the decency of their work, which is similar to the findings of Huang, Shen, and Yuan in 2021. However, job insecurity does not have a significant effect on organizational commitment, unlike what is assumed. Employees' insecurity about their jobs usually comes from their own factors about themselves, such as age, skills. On the other hand, it is usually easy for employees of SMEs to find jobs because they have lower expectations of themselves. It doesn't take much to get a good job, so they are willing to work. The reason for this may come from the fact that SMEs employees do not have much confidence and expectation in themselves.

(2) The effects of organizational commitment, organizational justice, decent work, and job insecurity on employee well-being at work

The R^2 of job well-being in this study reached 0.724, which shows that the variance can be well explained by the model's independent variables. Among these independent variables, organizational commitment has the greatest effect on job well-being than organizational justice, job insecurity, and labor decency. Its standardized regression coefficient is 0.469. The organizational commitment represents employees' recognition and trust in the organization and can be said to be a sign of people's loyalty to the organization. The results of this study are similar to Boyd and Nowell's study. When organizational commitment is high, employees' happiness at work is higher. This shows that the relationship between employees and the company is usually very stable in Taiwan SMEs. This is inseparable from the social and cultural atmosphere. More than 98% of the companies in Taiwan are small and medium-sized enterprises, where employees are close to their bosses and can easily understand the company's business situation. Most Taiwan employees are pure and simple, have high loyalty to the organization, have high commitment to the organization, are grateful for the work opportunities given by the organization, and are very empathetic to the organization.

(3) Job insecurity has no significant impact on organizational commitment

The results of this study found that even under the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic, job insecurity among Taiwanese SMEs employees did not have a significant effect on organizational commitment. Although the period of this survey coincided with the seriousness of the COVID-19 epidemic, many SMEs were faced with the threat of survival. Many companies are even keeping their employees without pay or making them redundant, but most of them do not feel unsafe at work. It is possible that the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak was not the result of poor corporate governance, and that employees can understand that the company had no choice but to act. On the other hand, employees who have a good relationship with the company expect that things will return to normal after the outbreak. Employees know in their hearts that this is a temporary situation and they still have expectations for the future. Therefore, employee psychological insecurity has no significant impact on organizational commitment.

(4) The results of the mediating effects

Organizational justice and decent work significantly affect employees' job well-being through organizational commitment, but job insecurity does not affect employees' job well-being through organizational commitment. The mediating effects once again prove the characteristics of Taiwan SMEs employees, who have high perceptions of organizational commitment and low job insecurity. It is possible that small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan treat their employees well in general, and that employees are more concerned about their personal feelings, such as the feeling of organizational justice and decent labor.

This study examines the factors affecting employees' job happiness during the COVID-19 period in Taiwan's SMEs and examines employees' perceptions of organizational commitment from the perspective of organizational

fairness, job insecurity, and the influence of labor aspects on job happiness. The results of the study revealed that the industry is flexible because of the large number of SMEs in Taiwan. When a company closes down due to COVID-19 factors, new companies will always be established. Although many companies are under significant pressure under COVID-19, employees still have a high level of organizational commitment to the company and a high sense of job happiness.

References

- Abid, G., Ahmed, S., Elahi, N. S., & Ilyas, S. (2020). Antecedents and mechanism of employee well-being for social sustainability: A sequential mediation. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 24, 79-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2020.06.011>
- Agarwal, P. (2021). Shattered but smiling: Human resource management and the wellbeing of hotel employees during COVID-19. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 93, 102765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102765>
- Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of occupational psychology*, 63(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>
- Blustein, D. L., Olle, C., Connors-Kellgren, A., & Diamonti, A. (2016). Decent work: A psychological perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 407. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00407>
- Bollen, K. A., & Stine, R. A. (1992). Bootstrapping goodness-of-fit measures in structural equation models. *Sociological methods & research*, 21(2), 205-229. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124192021002004>
- Boyd, N. M., & Nowell, B. (2020). Sense of community, sense of community responsibility, organizational commitment and identification, and public service motivation: A simultaneous test of affective states on employee well-being and engagement in a public service work context. *Public Management Review*, 22(7), 1024-1050. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2020.1740301>
- Brown, G. (2009). Claiming a corner at work: Measuring employee territoriality in their workspaces. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 29(1), 44-52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.05.004>
- Burhan, M., Salam, M. T., Abou Hamdan, O., & Tariq, H. (2021). Crisis management in the hospitality sector SMEs in Pakistan during COVID-19. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 98, 103037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.103037>
- Cao, Y., Liu, J., Liu, K., Yang, M., & Liu, Y. (2019). The mediating role of organizational commitment between calling and work engagement of nurses: A cross-sectional study. *International journal of nursing sciences*, 6(3), 309-314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2019.05.004>
- Chen, H., & Eyoum, K. (2021). Do mindfulness and perceived organizational support work? Fear of COVID-19 on restaurant frontline employees' job insecurity and emotional exhaustion. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 94, 102850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102850>
- Cohen, A. (2017). Organizational Commitment and Turnover: A Met A-Analysis. *Academy of management journal*.
- Cohen, A., & Diamant, A. (2019). The role of justice perceptions in determining counterproductive work behaviors. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(20), 2901-2924. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1340321>
- Cropanzano, R., Bowen, D., & Gilliland, S. (2007). The management of organizational justice. *Academy of Management Perspective*, 21, 34-48. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2007.27895338>
- Darvishmotevali, M., & Ali, F. (2020). Job insecurity, subjective well-being and job performance: The moderating role of psychological capital. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 87, 102462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102462>
- De Cremer, D., Brockner, J., Fishman, A., Van Dijke, M., Van Olffen, W., & Mayer, D. M. (2010). When do procedural fairness and outcome fairness interact to influence employees' work attitudes and behaviors? The moderating effect of uncertainty. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(2), 291. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017866>
- Diao, Y.-H., & Chen, C.-S. (2020). Research on the Relationship Between Job Competence and Job Well-Being in Service Industry—Based on the Mediating Effect of Job Insecurity. *International Business Research*, 13(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v13n1p1>
- Diener, E. (1984). Subjective well-being. *Psychol. Bull*, 95, 542-595. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.95.3.542>
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L. (1999). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological bulletin*, 125(2), 276. <https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/1999-10106-007>
- Duffy, R. D., Blustein, D. L., Diemer, M. A., & Autin, K. L. (2016). The psychology of working theory. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 63(2), 127. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000140>
- Duffy, R. D., Prieto, C. G., Kim, H. J., Raque-Bogdan, T. L., & Duffy, N. O. (2021). Decent work and physical health: a multi-wave investigation. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 127, 103544.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2021.103544>
- Etehadi, B., & Karatepe, O. M. (2019). The impact of job insecurity on critical hotel employee outcomes: The mediating role of self-efficacy. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 28(6), 665-689. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2019.1556768>
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39-50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378101800104>
- Frone, M. R. (2018). What happened to the employed during the Great Recession? A US population study of net change in employee insecurity, health, and organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 107, 246-260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2018.05.001>
- Gabčanová, I. (2011). The employees—the most important asset in the organizations. *Human Resources Management & Ergonomics*, 5(1), 30-33. http://frcatel.fri.uniza.sk/hrme/files/2011/2011_1_03.pdf
- Gorgenyi-Hegyessy, E., Nathan, R. J., & Fekete-Farkas, M. (2021). Workplace Health Promotion, Employee Wellbeing and Loyalty during Covid-19 Pandemic—Large Scale Empirical Evidence from Hungary. *Economies*, 9(2), 55. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9020055>
- Greenhalgh, L., & Rosenblatt, Z. (1984). Job insecurity: Toward conceptual clarity. *Academy of Management Review*, 9(3), 438-448. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1984.4279673>
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (1998). *Multivariate data analysis* (Vol. 5). Prentice hall Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Hanaysha, J. (2016). Testing the effects of employee engagement, work environment, and organizational learning on organizational commitment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 289-297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.139>
- Hartley, J., Jacobson, D., Klandermans, B., & Van Vuuren, T. (1990). *Job insecurity: Coping with jobs at risk*. Sage Publications Ltd. <http://oro.open.ac.uk/36773/>
- Heaney, C. A., Israel, B. A., & House, J. S. (1994). Chronic job insecurity among automobile workers: Effects on job satisfaction and health. *Social science & medicine*, 38(10), 1431-1437. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(94\)90281-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(94)90281-X)
- Holbrook Jr, R. L. (2002). Contact points and flash points: conceptualizing the use of justice mechanisms in the performance appraisal interview. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12(1), 101-123. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-4822\(01\)00053-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-4822(01)00053-5)
- Hou, C.-K. (2020). The effects of IT infrastructure integration and flexibility on supply chain capabilities and organizational performance: An empirical study of the electronics industry in Taiwan. *Information Development*, 36(4), 576-602. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266666919884352>
- Huang, G. h., Zhang, Y., Zhang, X., & Long, L. (2021). Job insecurity, commitment and proactivity towards the organization and one's career: Age as a condition. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 31(2), 532-552. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12322>
- Huang, W., Shen, J., & Yuan, C. (2021). How Decent Work Affects Affective Commitment Among Chinese Employees: The Roles of Psychological Safety and Labor Relations Climate. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 106907272111029673. <https://doi.org/10.1177/106907272111029673>
- Hussain, S., & Shahzad, K. (2021). Unpacking perceived organizational justice-organizational cynicism relationship: Moderating role of psychological capital. *Asia Pacific Management Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2021.03.005>
- ILO. (1999). Report of the director-general: Decent Work. Retrieved December 19 from <http://www.ilo.org/public/english/standards/relm/ilc/ilc87/rep-i.htm>
- ILO. (2020). Decent Work. International Labor Organization. Retrieved December 30 from <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/decent-work/lang--en/index.htm>
- Imamoglu, S. Z., Ince, H., Turkcan, H., & Atakay, B. (2019). The effect of organizational justice and organizational commitment on knowledge sharing and firm performance. *Procedia Computer Science*, 158, 899-906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.129>
- Jackson, D. L., Gillaspay Jr, J. A., & Purc-Stephenson, R. (2009). Reporting practices in confirmatory factor analysis: an overview and some recommendations. *Psychological methods*, 14(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0014694>
- Jain, P., Duggal, T., & Ansari, A. H. (2019). Examining the mediating effect of trust and psychological well-being on transformational leadership and organizational commitment. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-07-2018-0191>
- Jang, J., Lee, D. W., & Kwon, G. (2021). An analysis of the Influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 44(2), 146-154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2019.1672185>
- Jankelova, N., Joniakova, Z., Blstakova, J., & Nemethova, I. (2017). Readiness of human resource departments of agricultural enterprises for implementation of the new roles of human resource professionals. <http://repository.embuni.ac.ke/handle/123456789/1960>

- Jones, D. A., & Skarlicki, D. P. (2003). The Relationship Between Perceptions of Fairness and Voluntary Turnover Among Retail Employees 1. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 33(6), 1226-1243. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2003.tb01947.x>
- Jung, H. S., Jung, Y. S., & Yoon, H. H. (2021). COVID-19: The effects of job insecurity on the job engagement and turnover intent of deluxe hotel employees and the moderating role of generational characteristics. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 92, 102703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102703>
- Khan, K., Abbas, M., Gul, A., & Raja, U. (2015). Organizational justice and job outcomes: Moderating role of Islamic work ethic. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 126(2), 235-246. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10551-013-1937-2>
- Kim, J. S., Milliman, J. F., & Lucas, A. F. (2021). Effects of CSR on affective organizational commitment via organizational justice and organization-based self-esteem. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 92, 102691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102691>
- Konovsky, M. A. (2000). Understanding procedural justice and its impact on business organizations. *Journal of management*, 26(3), 489-511. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063\(00\)00042-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063(00)00042-8)
- Koo, B., Curtis, C., & Ryan, B. (2021). Examining the impact of artificial intelligence on hotel employees through job insecurity perspectives. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 95, 102763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102763>
- Lin, X. (2015). How does procedural justice climate influence individual outcomes? An affective perspective. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 32(3), 771-800. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10490-015-9421-4>
- Lu, Y., Wu, J., Peng, J., & Lu, L. (2020). The perceived impact of the Covid-19 epidemic: evidence from a sample of 4807 SMEs in Sichuan Province, China. *Environmental Hazards*, 19(4), 323-340. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17477891.2020.1763902>
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1(1), 61-89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
- Meyer, J. P., Paunonen, S. V., Gellatly, I. R., Goffin, R. D., & Jackson, D. N. (1989). Organizational commitment and job performance: It's the nature of the commitment that counts. *Journal of applied psychology*, 74(1), 152. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.74.1.152>
- Mohr, G. B. (2000). The changing significance of different stressors after the announcement of bankruptcy: A longitudinal investigation with special emphasis on job insecurity. *Journal of organizational Behavior*, 21(3), 337-359. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1379\(200005\)21:3<337::AID-JOB18>3.0.CO;2-G](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1379(200005)21:3<337::AID-JOB18>3.0.CO;2-G)
- Nunnally, J. C. (1994). Psychometric theory 3E. Tata McGraw-hill education.
- Ponnu, C., & Chuah, C. (2010). Organizational commitment, organizational justice and employee turnover in Malaysia. *African Journal of business management*, 4(13), 2676-2692. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM.9000442>
- Pradhan, R. K., & Hati, L. (2019). The measurement of employee well-being: development and validation of a scale. *Global Business Review*, 0972150919859101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150919859101>
- Rahman, A., Belas, J., Kliestik, T., & Tyll, L. (2017). Collateral requirements for SME loans: empirical evidence from the Visegrad countries. *Journal of business economics and management*, 18(4), 650-675. <https://doi.org/10.3846/16111699.2017.1357050>
- Riketta, M. (2002). Attitudinal organizational commitment and job performance: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 23(3), 257-266. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.141>
- Russo, D., Hanel, P. H., Altnickel, S., & van Berkel, N. (2021). Predictors of well-being and productivity among software professionals during the COVID-19 pandemic—a longitudinal study. *Empirical Software Engineering*, 26(4), 1-63. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-021-09945-9>
- Salas-Nicas, S., Moncada, S., Llorens, C., Morina, D., & Navarro, A. (2020). A complex view of perceived job insecurity: Relationship between three domains and their respective cognitive and affective components. *Safety Science*, 129, 104796. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104796>
- Small and Medium Enterprises Division, M. o. E. A. (2021). SMEs show resilience and are the cornerstone of economic stability and job creation. Small and Medium Enterprises Division, Ministry of Economic Affairs. Retrieved Nov 2 from <https://www.moeasmea.gov.tw/article-tw-2276-7454>
- Tett, R. P., & Meyer, J. P. (1993). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, turnover intention, and turnover: path analyses based on meta-analytic findings. *Personnel psychology*, 46(2), 259-293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1993.tb00874.x>
- Tseng, C.-C. (2010). The effects of learning organization practices on organizational commitment and effectiveness for small and medium-sized enterprises in Taiwan. University of Minnesota. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/477b75b89fbb7094c770722594c04fd1/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>
- Vignoli, E., Prudhomme, N., Terriot, K., Cohen-Scali, V., Arnoux-Nicolas, C., Bernaud, J.-L., & Lallemand, N. (2020). Decent work in France: Context, conceptualization, and assessment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*,

- 116, 103345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2019.103345>
- Wang, X., Guchait, P., Lee, J., & Back, K.-J. (2019). The importance of psychological safety and perceived fairness among hotel employees: The examination of antecedent and outcome variables. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 18(4), 504-528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332845.2019.1626964>
- Weziak-Bialowolska, D., Bialowolski, P., Sacco, P. L., VanderWeele, T. J., & McNeely, E. (2020). Well-being in life and well-being at work: Which comes first? Evidence from a longitudinal study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8, 103. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00103>
- Witte, H. D. (1999). Job insecurity and psychological well-being: Review of the literature and exploration of some unresolved issues. *European Journal of work and Organizational psychology*, 8(2), 155-177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/135943299398302>
- Yang, C.-C., & Chuang, H.-Y. (2020). The strategy for return to work after the COVID-19 pandemic on small and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 62(8), e471-e472. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000001926>
- Yeh, C.-H., & Chen, C.-Y. (2017). The Relationships among Pay Secrecy, Distributive Justice, and Job-Related Outcomes. *人力資源管理學報*, 17(3), 85-110. <https://doi.org/10.6147/JHRM.2017.1703.04>
- Yiing, L. H., & Ahmad, K. Z. B. (2009). The moderating effects of organizational culture on the relationships between leadership behaviour and organizational commitment and between organizational commitment and job satisfaction and performance. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730910927106>
- Zhou, Y. S. (2020). BCG Survey: How are companies responding to the epidemic? 12 Tips for Leaders. Bnext Media. Retrieved December 16 from <https://www.managertoday.com.tw/articles/view/59574>